

Educational Erosion: The Marginalization of Teachers Amidst Digital Distractions

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Abstract: The rapid advancement of digital technology in the field of education has completely transformed the education learning process and environment, they have introduced new challenges and opportunities. This article may explore the increasing influence of distractions, especially smartphones and other digital devices, the engagement of the students and their overall development. It may examine the important role of teachers to shape the social, academic, mental and emotional growth, focusing their role as role models, mentors, and try to facilitate their well-rounded development. The article is going to highlights that how the growth of technology has marginalized the role of teachers, it has also shifted the teacher-oriented learning process to student-centered, tech-based experiences. This kind of shift has generated a gap between both, reducing the traditional way of teachers to guide and support the students. The outcome of this change has created a negative impact on physical activity, mental health, social interaction, and educational motivation. To advocate these situations, the article guides for a balanced and proper approach to integrate the rapid growth of technology with the guidance of teachers, ensuring the harmony between both rather than replacing the role of teacher in education. In nutshell, the article emphasizes restoring the central role of teacher, focusing on the importance of social and human teachings and developing a proper educational system that can encourage academic success, socialization and holistic development of children.

Keywords - Technology, Children, Education, Teacher, Health issue

Introduction: In life, every stage of growth and development serves a specific purpose, and there are certain factors that are essential for the proper growth of children. Being innocent children, they are always unaware of the drastically impact of the digital instruments. As parents, teacher or guardian it is our sole duty to have a continuous track on their screen timing otherwise it may be fatal and critical in coming years. Research on child development consistently focuses that outdoor play is crucial for every child during the early stages of a child's life. It encourages not only physical growth but also enhances emotional and social interaction, creating a balanced and well-rounded person. Though, in the current situation of technological development, the natural process of growth and development has been challenged.

The speedy technological advancement has deeply reshaped various shades of modern life, and the field of education is not an exception. Technological innovation was introduced to enhance the

learning process with the aim of creating an effective and more progressive educational growth and development, but their outcomes have not been completely positive. The prompt rise of digital devices has decreased the physical activities of all the children, hindering their overall development. Real growth requires not only academic learning but also active participation of play, their physical exercise along with social interactions with peers and others, which nurture both physical and mental well-being. Unfortunately, in this new era, many children are increasingly confined indoors to their digital worlds, detached from social environments, and engaged in screen time that causes a range of negative consequences such as stress, anxiety, and other physical and mental health challenges. Being a sensitive parent, we also think of creating a proper way for our children. The article will explore the advantages and disadvantages along with the solution part that how we can save the children from such kind of technological environment. As Bill Gates has rightly said, “Technology is just a tool. In terms of getting the kids working together and motivating them, the teacher is the most important.” (Web)

The Rapid Change in Education

We should remember the pandemic situation and the starting phase of work from home culture and the same with the schools. How the students were asked to join the classes online and to complete their homework with the help of digital tools and websites. It was one of the main reasons for the speedy expansion of the entry of digitalization on a large scale. In the very beginning it was alright, but soon after the negative aspects started to be realized by society. It had more negative impact on the children where the parents were uneducated, or they did not control children while providing them with such devices. The growing phase of digital culture started ignoring the importance of teachers where teachers began marginalized, the role of teachers who used to be the true role model and mentor minimized their role, and the students realized the knowledge of google that responds to all their queries within a second. It was the reason to replace the google as their teacher instead of the real teacher.

The Teacher’s Role in Child’s Development and Learning

Again, if we remember our days in schools willingly and carefully, we used to listen to our teachers and follow them. The teachers used to check the homework, and, in some cases, they could use sticks to beat us. It was quite normal. By teaching the moral lessons, they guided us the social and cultural values, telling the stories of sculptures and the legends to help us to learn the human values as well. These activities not only connect us with the teacher and society but also guide us to the proper growth of life. We learn the moral values through those stories and the cultural heritage of our ancestors.

The teacher influences all the aspects of life that builds a systematic and holistic development of the student. Their mentoring and guidance always pave a path with discipline and morality and socializing them. The balance mental and emotional health and all the aspects of learning is taught by the teachers directly during the interaction in the classes. Dan Rather in his book *The Camera Never Blinks (1984)*, says, “The dream begins, most of the time, with a teacher who believes in you, who tugs and pushes and leads you on to the next plateau, sometimes poking you with a sharp stick called truth.” (Web)

Digital Distractions: Digitization in Education

Apart from the guidance of the teacher it is our responsibility to protect our children from digital devices. The students are highly interested to watch the social medial videos and clips that has prevailed everywhere on social media sites. There are no boundaries of the kinds of videos shared on social media that may have a negative impact on our children. The habit of watching rebels can destroy the mental, emotional and social life of our children and that can lead to fatal consequences

in the future. The best way is to give our time to our children, seat with them, talk to them, spending time with them can only help them in their development and we can prevent them slowly and help them to move towards the right platform of life. The alluring of online entertainment is very attractive, once we lose our control to our children they will be entangled again with distraction of social media or games, it is mandatory to track properly and foster them by our best parenting responsibilities.

The Marginalization of Teachers in the Digital Era

As there was a sudden shift from teacher-centered learning to student-driven during the pandemic, it spread so quickly that everyone became almost very fascinated with technology-mediated learning? It was the time when the authority of the teacher was challenged, and his influence started deteriorating in the class. His influence was sidelined by the digital devices and their frequent usage. The students started realizing that the apps and websites are more intelligent than the teachers in the classroom. But the entire social media captured their brain, they start studying on websites and slip into social media, the world of distraction. The worst thing about social media is that it captures the data of your interest or surfing and keep on arranging through AI the same data and finally it traps you in that circle.

Frankly speaking, even if you go to online platform, there is also a teacher who has created that the modules for the students and ultimately the credit goes to a teacher. It may be far better than the teacher teaching in the classroom, but they cannot socialize or create a comprehensive development. In fact, in coming years online platforms are going to capture this education industry completely. As online courses has already been started by several universities and these degrees are valid and easy to pass for the students.

I remember a chapter in class 9th "Beehive" Textbook (CBSE) Prose: "*The Fun They Had*" set in a future where the children are educated automatically by mechanical teachers at their home, they have completely replaced physical schools and human interaction. The moment when children Tommy and Margie found an old, physical printed book about the past schools, they become highly fascinated by knowing the idea of a school where social, traditional and school environment was different and the students used to learn from human teachers and study in the classroom with their classmates. Thus, the teachers have been sidelined by the digital devices in this ultra-modern age, and the continuity will change the education system to the next level. There are several negative effects on the students due to social sites, and they distract the students from face-to-face learning and the interaction with teachers and co-students. When a student studies in a group they learn by interaction with one another. Apart from this, they lack the concept of teamwork. It also decreases the physical activities of the students, and they spend more time to screen than going outside for outdoor activities. It is going to have a long-term impact on the mental health of the students and leads to anxiety and isolation issues due to digital interaction. It has lower engagement of the student and less participation in the school activities that increase the lack of motivation and learning. As Mark Van Doren has commented, "The art of teaching is the art of assisting discovery." (Web)

Balancing Digital Technology and Traditional Education System

In this era, no one can live without interacting with technology, its impact has become an inherent part of the school and its curriculum. As there is also a line by "Lord Buddha" to move on with the "middle way of life". It means we need to learn the balancing approach of the digitalization and the traditional education system where we can apply and utilize both the ways to get optimum value of both. The students can use the technology with the proper guidance of the teachers. The instruction of a teacher can be highly useful for the students, and they can find the right way or

perception to get the right track to use the digital modules. Technology can only enhance but can never replace the teacher. The mentorship and the interaction of a teacher will remain there, but it will be facilitated with the help of technology to grow the students in a better prospect and lead to the modern step of life. This rapid digitalization can empower and mostly provide the information or solution of the problems along with the proper help of the traditional teachers.

Reshaping the Teacher's Role in today's Digital Age

The change is inevitable, and it happens time to time in every aspect of our life. The field of teaching has also been the part of this change of the digital age where a teacher should change himself by learning the new technology and its implications. This not only improve the method of teaching but also enhance the regularity and the attention of the students in the classroom. There are several things that cannot be taught online, but those abstract things can be clearly dictated by the teacher if he uses both his traditional way and the digital platform. The interaction in a digital world has great importance to create an engaging and supportive learning environment for the students. The true potential of a teacher is to guide the students on how to make right and the optimum use of the devices and to what extent they can be dependent on them. Which kinds of measures are required for the parents to take care of their children while using the devices? There are certain limitations and there are customized services for the children and parents where they can watch and make a boundary for them for certain limits. The screen timing, the websites, the apps and kind of interaction should be controlled by the parents with the help and guidance of the teachers. This can help to create a proper balanced approach, and the relation may continuously sustain with them. The children are innovative, and innocent and it is our responsibility to nurture and enhance them for the right direction and achievements. As George Couros in his book “*The Innovator's Mindset: Empower Learning, Unleash Talent, and Lead a Culture of Creativity*” (2015) has kept his opinion, - “Technology will never replace great teachers, but technology in the hands of great teachers can be transformational.” (Web)

Conclusion:

Our aim is to restore the role of the teacher in this digital distraction where these devices has captured the mind of everyone. There is a need to reclaim the value of our respected teachers in this humdrum of digital-driven society. We need to focus on the human connections and values of mentorship to shape our children with the valuable motivation of the teachers. Our emphasis should be to create a balanced approach to our education system that generates holistic growth and development towards the success of our students. Life has two wheels, and it is mandatory to make a balance between both the wheels as learn the new ways but balance with our route to continue the right platform of success.

At last, I conclude with the statement of Lord Buddha: “Do not tighten the strings of the veena so much that they break, nor loosen them so much that no music comes—true harmony lies in balance.” (Web) In the same way, the students must be taught in a balanced manner, where both the teachers and the digital tools should contribute together. Only with such creative balance can we build real learning, and proper growth may take place.

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